

Ethics State-of-the-Art and Literature Review

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Executive summary

This deliverable provides a literature review of several areas of research and investigation in the field of ethics, broadly conceived, that are relevant to the topic areas of the GuestXR project. As the GuestXR project brings together research on virtual reality (VR) and VR systems with artificial intelligence (AI) and reinforcement machine learning techniques, as well as neuroscience and social psychology, the state-of-the-art provided in this deliverable includes discussion of the following areas:

- the ethics of AI;
- ethical considerations related to the development and use of VR systems and intelligent virtual environments (IVE), bringing ethical investigations of VR into dialogue with the ethics of social AI systems;
- value-sensitive design methodologies, to be iterated within the GuestXR project

The deliverable utilises a semi-systematic review approach. Semi-systematic reviews map dominant themes that have emerged over time, drawing attention to how topics have developed across different research traditions. This allows for the synthesis of multiple perspectives across several areas of research. Using this approach provides a broad overview of the main issues, and helps to make sense of complex and often contested topics. A semi-structured review can then be used as a decision aid. This review will serve as the knowledge basis for the development of an “ethics-by-design” approach that will be utilised throughout the project.

In relation to the development of AI and machine learning applications, this review loosely adopts a framework proposed by Carly Kind, director of the Ada Lovelace Institute. This framework looks at the development of the rapidly expanding field of AI ethics in three, now overlapping phases:

- Abstract guiding principles and norms generally derived from systematic approaches in philosophical ethics and applied ethics;
- More technically oriented approaches that look primarily at how interventions and work programmes led by computer scientists and developers can address questions concerning issues like fairness, bias, and accessibility. This approach operationalised many of the more abstract or high-level ethical concerns raised in the first phase, but also tended to reframe them as technical problems requiring technical solutions.
- A third phase has shifted the discussion of ethical AI towards more social and political questions relating to questions of justice, including “social justice, racial justice, economic justice, and environmental justice” (Kind, 2020). Within this phase, technologies are considered embedded in and

co-producing socio-technical systems. As such, it is also concerned with questions relating power and structure as well as high-level ethical concerns, legal constraints and technical “fixes”. The practical focus in this approach is on co-creation processes that involve affected individuals and communities at early stages of technological development and innovation processes, giving them voice and capacity for action within the design and application of technical systems.

The third phase is also characterised by the further development of Responsible Innovation and “by-design” approaches. These approaches also characterise the approach to ethics within the GuestXR project.

The European Commission’s Ethical Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and the related seven requirements produced by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG) nonetheless remain extremely important foundational guidelines for the development of ethics-by-design methodologies and practices within the GuestXR project.

Based on fundamental rights and ethical principles, the Guidelines list seven key requirements that AI systems should meet in order to be trustworthy:

1. Human agency and oversight
2. Technical robustness and safety
3. Privacy and Data governance
4. Transparency
5. Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness
6. Societal and environmental well-being
7. Accountability

These requirements are based on the fundamental rights elaborated in the European treaties and other foundational documents as well as foundational ethical principles.

Ethical and social consideration of VR systems are closely intertwined with technical, scientific and indeed philosophical questions about embodiment, immersion and presence within VR environments. Thus, ethical examination of VR systems and environments has evolved alongside technical, psychological and sociological investigations. An initial focus has been on potential harms to individuals or vulnerable groups in VR environments – and how to prevent them. This focus has addressed questions concerning discrimination, stereotyping, anti-social behaviour such as sexual harassment as well as accessibility relating to equipment and the affordances within VR environments.

As the potential use of VR environments in various arenas of social life has increased and with many companies now eyeing the commercial potentials of these technologies, the nascent field of VR ethics has followed the development of AI ethics in starting to increasingly take into consideration broader socio-political questions relating to the governance of immersive virtual environments.

As the possibilities for individuals to spend greater amounts of time within VR environments (for professional, leisure, and commercial activities) continues to increase, the field of VR ethics has also begun to explore how habits and affinities

developed within VR environments might transfer into physical reality. This has opened up further possibilities for the use of VR, such as in therapeutic contexts. The growing potential of VR and the expanding scope of use applications has made the necessity for serious ethical consideration and upstream value-sensitive intervention increasingly important.

The GuestXR project, for this reason, has committed to the implementation of ethics-by-design approaches within the scientific work programme of the project. This deliverable will be followed by further guidelines for implementation of ethics-by-design methods and processes. These guidelines will therefore build, at least in part, upon the initial review of ethical and related literature in this deliverable.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information Sheet.....	2
Executive summary	3
List of tables	7
List of abbreviations	8
Introduction.....	9
1 Creating an IVRS: GuestXR.....	11
2 The Evolution of AI Ethics (In a Nutshell).....	13
3 Methodology	15
4 Ethical Principles Designed to Shape Design and Development.....	16
5 Technological Affordances and Related Ethical Concerns	24
5.1 Intelligent Virtual Agents	24
5.2 Embodiment, Immersion, and Presence	25
6 Critical Concerns Regarding Emerging Ethical Issues	28
6.1 Affect, Persuasion, and Empathy	28
6.2 Accessibility, Inclusion, and Exclusion	30
6.3 Phenomenology and Political Ontology: avenues of potential future investigations into the politics of VR and IVRS	32
6.3.1 The realness of VR worlds.....	32
6.3.2 Deception within IVRS	34
6.3.3 Privacy and Private government in and of IVRS	35
7 Ethics by, in, and for Design	37
8 Conclusions	42
9 References	43

List of tables

Table 1: 7 Requirements for Trustworthy AI	17
Table 2: Ethical Guidelines in VR.....	18
Table 3: Comparison of Ethical Guidelines for AI and VR	19
Table 4: Distinguishing between the research ethics of VR and foreseeable risks	20
Table 5: Summary of seven factors supporting AI4SG and the corresponding best practices	22
Table 6: 8 Grand Challenges for VSD from the 2016 Lorentz Workshop.....	40

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4SG	Artificial Intelligence for Social Good
AR	Augmented Reality
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
DSA	Digital Services Act
EU	European Union
GuestXR	Project Name
HCI	Human Computer Interaction
HMD	Head-Mounted Display
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
IVA	Intelligent Virtual Agent
IVE	Intelligent Virtual Environment
IVRS	Intelligent Virtual Reality System
PR	Physical Reality
RI	Responsible Innovation
VE	Virtual Environment
VR	Virtual Reality
VSD	Value Sensitive Design
XR	Extended Reality

Introduction

In 2021, the term “metaverse” was shortlisted by the Collins Dictionary as its word of the year. A portmanteau of the Greek term *meta* and the English word *universe*, the notion of the metaverse was initially coined in the early 1990s to refer to the notion of an immersive digital environment separate from the physical world. Today, Tim Bieber, CEO of XR Immersive Tech, suggests that the metaverse describes “a network of connected and social virtual reality experiences, facilitated by combining head-mounted displays (HMD), such as those created by Oculus and HTC, with virtual environments to allow users to feel present and immersed inside the experiences”.

The rapid development of “intelligent virtual environments” (IVEs) - like the metaverse - has been possible due to advances in technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of things (IoT), Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), 3D modelling, and spatial and edge computing. The increased accessibility and availability of HMDs has fuelled interest in VR, in 2021 alone almost 10 million VR devices were shipped worldwide and the VR market is expected to continue expanding at a compound annual growth rate of about 15% until 2030. As a result, IVEs are being developed by a variety of stakeholders for a range of purposes, from entertainment and gaming, to career development and education.

The goal of the GuestXR project is to develop an IVE with an integrated machine learning agent - the “Guest” - that will help facilitate problem solving and pro-social behaviour, allowing its users to work together towards specific goals. But because IVEs rely on new ways of integrating different forms of advanced computing, such as AI and VR, little is yet known about their potential ethical implications. Given that there has been a great deal of excitement surrounding the potential of IVEs, it is important to remember that new and emerging technologies often bring unforeseen and/or potentially undesirable consequences.

Drawing attention to these sorts of issues, the notion of “responsible innovation” (RI) has gained traction in both academic and policy circles in recent years (see Shanley, 2021; De Saille, 2015). Broadly speaking, RI refers to efforts to identify the ethical and societal aspects of technological innovations early in the design and development process so that these can be considered and evaluated by a broad array of potential stakeholders (see e.g. Owen, Stilgoe & Macnaghten, 2013). Drawing on our own experiences embedding RI in a multidisciplinary consortium project (Pansera, Owen, Meacham & Kuh, 2020), where we encouraged practices aimed at anticipation, reflexivity and deliberation in sometimes creative and innovative ways, we introduce the value sensitive design (VSD) approach as a methodology for implementing RI in the context of the GuestXR project.

The primary aim of this review is to map scholarly discussions regarding the potential ethical implications of IVEs and as such to provide a starting point for early engagement with these issues within the context of the GuestXR project. Drawing upon a growing list of academic publications addressing key public and ethical issues in the fields of AI and VR respectively, this review analyses these publications and summarises the most important issues that could emerge when AI and VR converge. We will begin by providing some further information about the development of IVEs, or, more specifically in the context of GuestXR, “intelligent virtual reality systems” (IVRS). We then provide a short overview of the evolution of AI ethics and describe the methodology used in order to conduct the review before offering a snapshot of the most relevant ongoing discussions across AI and VR. This section concludes with a more exploratory discussion concerning some of the political questions that may be raised by pervasive use of IVRS for commercial, social and political interactions. This discussion remains highly speculative. In the final section we discuss the importance of approaches that are commonly labelled as ethics by, in, and for design, introducing “value-sensitive design” (VSD) as one example of a methodology for integrating ethical deliberation and reflection throughout the design and development process. Questions concerning data management and data protection from a legal perspective are not addressed in this review (see deliverable D7.2 Initial Data Management Plan). We have also not addressed, in the first iteration of this review, questions pertaining to wearable sensors that are generally considered to fall within the domain of the nascent field of neuroethics (If appropriate these questions will be addressed in deliverables 5.5, 5.6 or 5.12).

1 Creating an IVRS: GuestXR

Though the terms virtual environment (VE) and virtual reality (VR) are often used interchangeably, VE refers to the digitally generated environment that the user of VR occupies, while VR is the system which serves as an interface between the user and said environment (Laukkanen et al., 2004). VEs rely on a set of advanced interface tools and techniques that enable the user to be immersed within the system. VEs are made up of virtual places, virtual objects, and virtual characters, where autonomous users can navigate around the environment, examining it from different points of view whilst interacting with objects and other real or virtual agents (Osório et al., 2005).

The GuestXR project seeks to integrate a machine learning agent into a VE, so as to explore the use of an intelligent (AI) entity in facilitating particular outcomes, allowing interactions of different types between VE components whilst also improving the realism and usability of VR systems. The guiding idea of the GuestXR project is to help people achieve specific goals within VE meeting spaces, by providing a socially interactive, multisensory platform that can bring people together through an immersive, synchronous experience.

In the early 2000s, Ruth Aylett and her colleagues coined the terms Intelligent Virtual Environment (IVE) and Intelligent Virtual Reality System (IVRS) to refer to the convergence of different branches of advanced computing, specifically AI and VR. Luck and Aylett (2000) suggest that as a result of the growing availability of graphics software, increases in processing power, and the maturation of AI technologies, at the turn of the century researchers interested in VEs and advanced graphics began “seeking to progress beyond visually compelling but essentially empty environments to incorporate other aspects of physical reality that require intelligent behaviour” (p. 1).

According to Aylett and Cavazza (2001), the term IVE encompasses a broad range of topics and research areas, however IVRS refers more specifically to systems that aim at integrating AI techniques, embedding intelligence in the system architecture by incorporating AI algorithms into the system itself. The creation of IVRS therefore involves using “AI technologies to improve the user interfacing, the virtual reality system and the believability of the contents of virtual worlds” (Laukkanen et al., 2004, p. 3). Introducing an AI layer into VEs not only adds a problem-solving component in terms of configuration, but also requires building a knowledge level which can support conceptual scene representation as well as “describing causal behaviours in the virtual environment” and “enhancing interactivity, i.e. by recognising user interaction in terms of high-level actions to determine adaptive behaviour from the system” (Aylett and Cavazza, 2001, pp. 2-3).

Given the high level of complexity involved, the development of IVRS represents an interdisciplinary challenge which involves concepts and techniques from a number of different fields including: computer science, computer graphics, human-computer interaction (HCI), robotics, psychology, behavioural studies, human anatomy, electronics, optics, physics, audio systems, acoustics, psychoacoustics, and many other knowledge areas (Osório et al., 2005; Laukkanen et al., 2004).

In the context of GuestXR, the project will draw upon neuroscience, social psychology, philosophy, and ethics. The Guest will be designed to perform different multisensory actions in order to elicit particular emotive states and stimulate a relaxed, collaborative atmosphere. These multisensory actions may vary from fairly minor modifications to the environment, such as changing the background music or weather, to more explicit interventions aimed at disrupting escalating interactions, such as introducing a problem which requires group cooperation or increasing the physical distance between participants.

To date, discussions regarding issues at the interface of AI and VEs have largely concerned tools, techniques, and systems across issues such as physical and cognitive agents, autonomy, and virtual worlds (Aylett and Luck, 2000). For example, Osório et al. (2005) provide an overview of several aspects related to the development of IVRS, such as VE modelling - "including the addition of 'intelligent information' into the environment" and agent and group simulations - "including environment interaction, scripts, behaviours and agent control architectures used in order to accomplish a specific task" (p. 58). However, despite IVRS having been in development for a number of years, what remains absent from the discussion so far is sustained engagement with the ethics of IVRS as a not new, but still emerging technology.

Before mapping the scholarly discussions regarding the potential ethical implications of IVRS, in the next section we first provide an overview of the evolution of ethical AI, which will provide the backdrop against which we organise the remaining discussion.

2 The Evolution of AI Ethics (In a Nutshell)

Though debates about the ethical dimensions of VR have taken place since the early 1990s (Steuer, 1994), since the mid-2010s, the rapid expansion of the VR marketplace has given new life to a range of novel ethical issues concerning the risks and dangers associated with the widespread use of VR (Cotton, 2021). With the development of domestic motion-sensitive headsets, each generation of hardware becomes more mobile and cost-effective (Ramirez et al, 2020). That being said, unlike AI, VR technologies are not yet a part of the average person's lived reality. When it comes to AI, day-to-day examples are so subtle we barely notice: whenever our phones autocorrect our text, or a streaming platform suggests what we might like next, AI algorithms constantly guide and steer our decision making. AI is embedded in both the private and public sectors, within standard business processes across various industries, from financial services to healthcare, as well as in the public safety arena.

Given the rise of AI across all spheres of private and public life, interest in the design and development of “ethical AI” has exploded in recent years. Carly Kind, Director of the Ada Lovelace Institute, describes three waves of ethical AI in this time. Kind (2020) suggests that the first was defined largely by philosophers and ethicists who created principles and guidelines at the behest of policymakers and tech developers. Essentially, the development of codes and standards was seen as an important and necessary response to increasing concerns about the potential risks and threats of AI. However, whereas the first wave bypassed questions of fairness and injustice, thereby failing to problematize adequately AI's broader societal implications, the second wave specifically addressed risks and ethical harms including bias and non-discrimination.

Led primarily by computer scientists, the second wave promoted the use of technical interventions, effectively reframing ethical problems as technical ones. By separating social problems from technical systems, second wave efforts narrowed the scope of ethical concerns, producing tools and metrics that were incapable of reflecting larger, underlying systemic issues. According to Kind, whilst both the first and second waves did help to operationalise concepts like explainability and fairness, the role of big tech companies in shaping these efforts has led many to see the first wave as “ethics washing” and the second wave as the co-optation of socially conscious computer scientists.

Around the turn of the current decade however, a third wave emerged, which saw the focus of ethical AI turn towards justice—“social justice, racial justice, economic justice, and environmental justice”. As Kind puts it, the third wave eschewed the term “ethical AI” in favour of “just AI”. Characteristics of third wave ethical AI is that it is practical, rather than conceptual; it is concerned with issues of power and structure, rather than legal constraints or technical fixes; and it is focused on practices of co-creation, on “AI by and for the people”. The focus in the third wave has been on how to create “human centred AI” (see e.g. Shneiderman, 2021; Auernhammer, 2020), reflecting a “shift in the gaze of ethical AI studies away from the technical towards the *socio-technical*” (Kind, 2020, emphasis ours).

Given that the GuestXR project weaves together state of the art developments in both AI and VR, we are interested in points at which the ethical implications of these two fields converge and diverge. In what follows we will therefore map the possible ethical implications involved in the creation of IVRS. Taking Kind's observations as our cue, we will map discussions relevant to the development of IVRS across both the AI and VR communities according to literature that deals with:

8. Ethical principles designed to shape design and development;
9. Technological affordances and related ethical concerns,
10. Critical concerns regarding emerging ethical issues.

Having identified some of the key issues which are likely to emerge in the context of IVRS, we will then introduce Value Sensitive Design (VSD) as an approach to ethics-by-design based upon co-creation methodologies. Before we explore these three themes in more detail, we first provide a brief outline of the methodology that was followed in putting together this review.

3 Methodology

Insofar as this review brings together research on AI and VR, both of which have been conceptualised differently and studied across various disciplines, reflecting a variety of different standpoints and perspectives, a semi-systematic review approach was adopted. Conducting a semi-systematic review entails mapping dominant themes which have emerged over time, drawing attention to how topics have developed across different research traditions (Snyder, 2009). Adopting this strategy enables the creation of meta-narratives which synthesise multiple perspectives, providing a broad overview of the main issues, helping to make sense of complex and often contested topics (Wong et al., 2013). Semi-systematic reviews rely on methods commonly used within qualitative research, particularly thematic and content analysis. These techniques provide a means for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns across a broad selection of texts (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Semi-systematic reviews are therefore particularly useful when it comes to detecting themes or common issues in relation to a particular research problem, in this case, identifying the relevant scholarly discussions in relation to the potential ethical implications of IVRS.

Whereas systematic literature reviews involve following a specific set of steps designed to answer a narrow research question, the semi-systematic review process is more exploratory and can therefore be tailored towards specific projects (Wong et al., 2013). Semi-systematic reviews involve making judgements and as such the approach cannot be prescribed through adherence to a checklist. However, Wong et al. (2013) do describe a number of guiding principles including: pragmatism, pluralism, historicity, contestation, reflexivity, and peer review which can be used to help ensure the transparency of the research process. By way of an example, the principle of pragmatism refers to the notion that the selection of what to include is not self-evident, but that the reviewer should be guided by what is likely to enable sense-making for the intended audience.

Following Wong et al.'s advice we first undertook an initial "territory mapping" exercise. This involved research using informal, unstructured methods, browsing libraries and internet databases, talking to colleagues within the GuestXR project, and consulting with experts and stakeholders. This scoping step is an essential part of a semi-systematic review as it helps to provide an overview of the different research traditions and literatures relevant to the topic of interest. Having identified which areas of the AI and VR discourses were most relevant in the context of IVRS, we next compared and contrasted findings from these different traditions to build a rich picture of the topic from multiple angles. As discussed earlier, we have focused in particular on ethical principles, technological affordances, critical concerns, and design methodologies. Though we make no claim to be in any way exhaustive, we hope to shine a light on examples of key ethical issues emerging in the context of IVRS.

4 Ethical Principles Designed to Shape Design and Development

The late 2010s saw the publication of numerous AI guidelines and codes of conduct, produced largely by ad hoc expert committees. Consisting largely of normative recommendations, these guidelines primarily define principles and values to shape the development and use of AI (for comprehensive reviews see Attard-Frost, De los Ríos & Walters, 2022; Hagendorff, 2020; and Jobin, Ienca & Vayena, 2019). In their analysis of 84 guidelines, Jobin, Ienca, and Vayena (2019) suggest that the largest producers of these documents have been private companies, followed by government agencies and research institutions. The USA and the UK account for more than a third of the documents, with the vast majority being produced in the global north. Whilst no single ethical principle appears across the entire corpus of documents, Jobin et al suggest that the predominance of “transparency”; “justice & fairness”; “non-maleficence”; “responsibility”; and “privacy” signal that global convergence around core ethical values does appear to be emerging. In another review, this time of 47 guidelines, Attard-Frost, De los Ríos, and Walters (2022) point out that these principles tend to “focus disproportionately on issues of algorithmic decision-making”. They argue that as a result, the political and economic implications of AI business practices are typically gravely underrepresented.

Whether within academia, policy making, or the media, discussions concerning ethical AI typically begin by establishing just such a list of ethical values (Stahl et al, 2022; see Floridi et al. 2018 for a comparative analysis). For example, the EU high-level expert group on AI ethics (for a critical review see Veale, 2020) outlines 7 requirements (see table 1) for trustworthy AI which include: human agency and oversight; technical robustness and safety; privacy and data governance; transparency; diversity, non-discrimination and fairness; societal and environmental well-being; and accountability (AI HELG, 2020). Despite these requirements covering a wide range of issues however, the opacity of AI systems has meant that increasingly the focus has been on values such as “explicability”, “transparency”, “traceability”, and “accountability” (Umbrello & van der Poel, 2021; Floridi et al, 2018).

Requirement	Description
Human agency and oversight	AI systems should not undermine human autonomy but rather be designed in accordance with fundamental human rights so as to enable users to make choices aligned with their goals.
Technical robustness and safety	Including resilience to attack and security breaches. AI systems must be reliable and mitigate vulnerabilities at every level, including data, modelling and infrastructure.
Privacy and data governance	AI systems must guarantee privacy and data protection throughout their lifecycle. Data must not be used to discriminate. Protocols for the governance of data access are therefore essential.
Transparency	Including traceability, explainability, and communication. This requirement is concerned with the entire operation of the system in terms of its development, function, performance, limitations, etc.
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	Fairness and inclusion are essential in fostering trust in AI systems. Participation can therefore help to ensure that AI systems are user-centric and accessible and that datasets do not reproduce historical bias.
Societal and environmental wellbeing	AI systems must be designed with long-term societal and environmental impacts in mind. Given the potential for unintended and unforeseen consequences to emerge, AI systems should be evaluated critically at every stage of the life cycle.
Accountability	AI systems require mechanisms to ensure accountability from design and development through to deployment and use.

Table 1: 7 Requirements for Trustworthy AI (AI HLEG, 2019)

In contrast to AI guidelines, VR guidelines and codes of conduct are still largely speculative and anticipatory (Kenwright, 2019; Spiegel, 2018; Madary & Metzinger, 2016). There has been little political or public debate on the implications of VR technologies (Kool et al., 2018). In proposing a new code of ethics for VR, Ramirez et al. (2020) therefore build upon the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) and the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers' (IEEE) existing ethics codes, as professional organisations with whom VR developers are most likely to be affiliated. They highlight ethical issues that are unique or at least different within VR, including data collection and privacy; content; nudging; user experience; dissociation; and the special case of children. Given these risks, Ramirez et al. suggest that “as these technologies become more deeply integrated into the everyday fabric of our social, political, and educational institutions and as they become a part of the work-environment, we must make sure that such new developments are met with equally new and important ethical constraints” (p. 11). In that their code suggests that ethical considerations should be built into the design process from an early stage, it reinforces the need to integrate approaches such as VSD.

Given the comprehensive character of VR, the potential influence upon human behaviour both in the virtual and physical worlds raises ethical concerns in relation to both psychological and physical well-being (Madary & Metzinger, 2016).

Drawing upon ethical guidelines in the field of psychology and research on the ethical challenges in VR (see Ramirez & LaBarge, 2018; Pan & Hamilton, 2018; Chirokoff, 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016), Bliznyuk (2019) outlines seven principles for the use of VR (see table 2).

Principle	Description
Equivalence principle	If it would be wrong to allow a person to have an experience of something in the real world, then it would be wrong to allow a person a virtually real analogue of that experience. As a simulation's likelihood of inducing virtually-real experiences in its subject increases, so too should the justification for the use of the simulation
Non-maleficence	No experiment should be conducted using VR with the foreseeable consequence that it will cause involuntary suffering or serious or lasting harm to a subject
Privacy	Users and participants ought to be made aware of the data being collected and how that data will be stored. Researchers must ensure informed consent and prevent the misuse of gathered data
Informed consent	Experiment participants should be informed that VR could have lasting and potentially unknown influences on their behaviour
Preservation of autonomy	Creating a false sense of agency is a violation of individual autonomy if it is non-beneficent. Manipulating agency must therefore be considered carefully in the context of VR
Transparency	Researchers must remind participants of the experimental nature of emerging technologies. They should be careful not to over promise or provide false hope with regards to the applications of VR
Dual use	Technology can be used for something other than its intended purpose, i.e. for military applications

Table 2: Ethical Guidelines in VR (Bliznyuk, 2019)

Shared principles with AI (see table 3) include transparency, non-maleficence, and privacy, whilst additional principles include the “equivalence principle”; “informed consent”; “preservation of autonomy”; and “dual use” (pp. 2-3).

7 Requirements for Trustworthy AI (AI HLEG, 2019)	VR Design Principles (Bliznyuk, 2019)
Human Agency and Oversight	Preservation of Autonomy
Technical Robustness and Safety	Not Addressed
Privacy and Data Governance	Privacy
Transparency	Transparency
Diversity, Non-Discrimination, and Fairness	Non-Maleficence
Societal and Environmental Well-being	Not Addressed
Accountability	Not Addressed
Not Addressed	Equivalence Principle
Not Addressed	Informed Consent
Not addressed	Dual Use

Table 3: Comparison of Ethical Guidelines for AI and VR

Madary and Metzinger (2016) provide perhaps the most comprehensive consideration of ethics in VR, in that they distinguish between the research ethics of VR and the issues that arise in the context of use, in order to demonstrate the entanglement of values and principles with possible longer-term impacts (see table 4). For example, because long-term immersion is considered a foreseeable risk, they highlight the importance of informed consent with regards to the lasting psychological effects of VR. In this way, they highlight how ethical issues and concerns might be translated into best practices. As Radziwill (2019) suggests, Madary and Metzinger’s recommendations make clear the extent to which both context and intent must be factored into ethical frameworks.

Research Ethics of VR (p. 19)	Foreseeable Risks (pp. 13-18)
Non-maleficence	Long-term immersion
Informed consent	Neglect of embodied interaction and the physical environment
Transparency and media ethics	Risky content
Dual use	Privacy
Internet research	X
Limitations of a code of conduct	X

Table 4: Distinguishing between the research ethics of VR and foreseeable risks (Madary and Metzinger, 2016)

A report on Responsible VR published by the Dutch Rathenau Institute (2020) distinguishes between foreseeable risks of VR and measures geared towards curtailing those risks. They organise public and ethical issues associated with VR according to four clusters: physical and mental risks, social risks, abuse of power, and legal risks (see figure 1). The regulation measures they outline include: launching a public debate on the ethics of VR, establishing frameworks for integrating VR into Society, informing and protecting VR consumers properly, and studying the long-term effects of VR (p. 7).

Figure 1: Four Risk Clusters in Consumer VR Use (Rathenau, 2020, p. 6)

Crucially, as Hagendorff (2020) argues, the existence of regulatory guidelines and codes of conduct alone does not guarantee their impact. In his analysis of 22 AI guidelines, Hagendorff suggests that within AI, for example, engagement with ethical guidelines is low; reading them has little effect on the decision-making of software developers; and that ultimately guidelines and codes of conduct reinforce the notion of AI ethics as being “extraneous, as surplus or some kind of ‘add-on’ to technical concerns” (p. 114). Hagendorff confirms that checkbox guidelines and codes of conduct do often seem to serve as marketing strategies—or ethics washing—in that they fail to actually integrate relevant ethical issues and concerns throughout the research and development process.

In an effort to move beyond generating sets of principles towards the formulation of best practices and concrete recommendations for new strategies, the AI for social good (AI4SG) approach outlines 7 ethical factors (see table 5) which relate to one or more of the 5 ethical principles of AI (which the authors define as beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, autonomy, and explicability) (Floridi et al., 2018).

Factors	Corresponding Best Practices	Corresponding Ethical Principles
Falsifiability and incremental deployment	Identify falsifiable requirements and test them in incremental steps from the lab to the “outside world”	Nonmaleficence
Safeguards against the manipulation of predictors	Adopt safeguards which (i) ensure that non-causal indicators do not inappropriately skew interventions, and (ii) limit, when appropriate, knowledge of how inputs affect outputs from AI4SG systems, to prevent manipulation	Nonmaleficence
Receiver-contextualised intervention	Build decision-making systems in consultation with users interacting with and impacted by these systems; with understanding of users’ characteristics, the methods of coordination, the purposes and effects of an intervention; and with respect for users’ right to ignore or modify interventions	Autonomy
Receiver-contextualised explanation and transparent purposes	Choose a Level of Abstraction for AI explanation that fulfils the desired explanatory purpose and is appropriate to the system and the receivers; then deploy arguments that are rationally and suitably persuasive for the receiver to deliver the explanation; and ensure that the goal (the system’s purpose) for which an AI4SG system is developed and deployed is knowable to receivers of its outputs by default	Explicability
Privacy protection and data subject consent	Respect the threshold of consent established for the processing of datasets of personal data	Nonmaleficence; Autonomy
Situational fairness	Remove from relevant datasets variables and proxies that are irrelevant to an outcome, except when their inclusion supports inclusivity, safety, or other ethical imperatives	Justice
Human-friendly semanticisation	Do not hinder the ability for people to semanticise (that is, to give meaning to, and make sense of) something	Autonomy

Table 5: Summary of Seven Factors Supporting AI4SG and Corresponding Best Practices (from Floridi et al., 2020, p. 1790)

According to Floridi et al. (2018), these 7 factors are “ethically robust and pragmatically applicable” in that they can be clearly formulated and directly translated into design requirements. Broadly speaking, AI4SG refers to “the design, development, and deployment of AI systems in ways that (i) prevent, mitigate or resolve problems adversely affecting human life and/or the wellbeing of the natural world, and/or (ii) enable socially preferable and/or environmentally sustainable developments” (p. 1774).

According to Umbrello and van de Poel (2021), whilst the AI4SG approach has made significant headway, “its underlying principles remain fuzzy” (p. 284). At the same time however, what the AI4SG approach does reflect is a move towards supporting and incentivizing best practices. Crucially, as Gianni, Lehtinen, and Nimiten (2022) point out, best practices must also integrate civil society into the selection of AI objectives. Unlike most ethical guidelines, which only “timidly” address this issue, they propose a framework of democratic experimentation in order to help strengthen the active role of society when it comes to discussing the design and development of AI systems.

5 Technological Affordances and Related Ethical Concerns

5.1 Intelligent Virtual Agents

According to Aylett and Cavazza (2001), the biggest single area in which AI and VEs overlap is that of virtual humans and synthetic characters. Intelligent agents can be characterised according to their type (e.g. Franklin & Graesser, 1996), their level of sophistication (e.g. Jennings & Wooldridge, 1996), their task type (e.g. Brenner et al., 1998; Sycara et al., 1996; Maes, 1994; Reilly & Bates, 1992), their interaction style (Nwana, 1996), their control architecture (Aylett & Cavazza, 2001), as well as their degree of autonomy (Thalmann, 1996). Aylett and Cavazza (2001) adopt the term Intelligent Virtual Agent (IVA) to broadly denote any intelligent, embodied entity within IVRS. An overarching definition of IVAs could include a wide range of technologies including synthetic agents, virtual actors, virtual humans, conversation agents, and digital assistants (See review by Burden & Savin-Baden, 2019). Definitions of these systems vary depending on their capabilities, domain, and level of embodiment (Ruane, Birhane & Ventreque, 2019).

IVAs can draw upon a range of AI technologies including natural language processing, machine translation, speech recognition, machine learning, or knowledge representation (Russel, 2010). Resisting the temptation to refer to problematic behaviourist models (typified by Turing's Imitation Game), Reader and Savin-Baden (2019) suggest that working definitions of IVAs should include that they are software programs modelled on human capabilities such as behaviour, emotion, autonomy, and interaction (p. 291).

Despite the use of some IVAs being widespread (e.g. digital assistants and chatbots), little is yet known about their long term impact (Reader & Savin-Baden, 2019). It is also unclear what lies ahead in terms of their possible application in teaching, research, business, or government (Burden & Savin-Baden, 2019). Ethical considerations unique to machine-human conversation have yet to become de facto considerations in the design and development of IVAs, nor are they taken into account in existing guidelines (Ruane, Birhane, & Ventreque, 2019; Reader & Savin-Baden, 2019).

As Reader & Savin-Baden (2019) point out some of the issues raised within robot ethics also apply to IVAs (on robot ethics see Wallach & Asaro, 2020; Lin, Abney & Jenkins, 2017; and Malle, 2016). For example, "ethical questions about how humans should design, deploy, and treat robots" as well as "what moral capacities a robot should have" (p. 291). Reflections on how the technological features of robots shape user experience and engagement in terms of their behavioural authenticity, emotional connectivity, and responsiveness are also relevant (Borenstein and Arkin, 2016; Savin-Baden et al., 2013). Studies show that agency attribution is key to both robots and IVAs with voice and affect playing a key role in supporting trust (Savin-Baden et al., 2013; Reeves & Nass, 1996). While there are interesting parallels with concerns in robotics, there are also important differences. For example, IVAs are not dependent upon physical forces and materials, they don't rely on gears and motors. As a result, there is much more flexibility when it comes to their design.

In the context of IVAs, Burden & Savin-Baden (2019) suggest that the establishment of trust requires a high degree of “humanness” including presence, responsiveness, and sociality. Different technologies and approaches have been used to improve humanness through increased functionality in terms of speech recognition, avatar realism, communication, expression etc. However, different issues can arise depending on whether a system’s design begins with natural language processing or machine learning. For example, focusing on the technical aspects of language processing often neglects the nuance of conversation as well as the role of social, cultural, and contextual factors in shaping communication practices. Similarly, whilst machine learning approaches might be useful in specific areas of functionality (e.g. recognizing speech or patterns of behaviour), they are hugely dependent upon the type and the amount of data that they are given to work with (Burden & Savin-Baden, 2019).

The embodiment of IVAs within IVRS also has ethical implications. In contrast to physical robots which are bound by physical laws, the question that arises in the context of VR is in how far IVAs should be subject to the same limitations and drives as physical humans in the physical world. According to Burden and Savin-Baden (2019), “one of the key tenets of embodied AI is that the AI needs those limitations in order to make sense of the world we live in” (p. 153). Of course virtual worlds could consist of imaginative, idealised scenes, or more straightforward representations of our everyday environments. Drawing upon discussions about physical public spaces, it seems safe to assume that the way in which virtual public spaces will come together will be largely driven by the relative diversity (or lack thereof) of their designers (Bonsiepe, 2016) and users (Carmona, 2018). While much of the research within VR has focused on improving the embodiment, immersion, and presence of the user, the extent to which virtual public spaces mediate those effects deserves further attention. The ways in which particular norms and values guide the design and development of virtual public spaces require careful consideration, especially given the potential that IVAs will become regular collaborators and co-creators in the design and development of virtual worlds.

5.2 Embodiment, Immersion, and Presence

According to Taylor (2002), avatars provide the “material out of which relationships and interactions are *embodied*” (p. 41). Avatars therefore provide a crucial “access point” through which users “intersect with a technological object and embody themselves, making the virtual environment and the variety of phenomenon it fosters real” (p. 41). In relation to VR applications, Kiltner, Groten, and Slater (2012) refer to a “sense of embodiment” proposing a working definition which includes: a sense of self-location, a sense of agency, and a sense of body ownership (p. 373). According to the authors, visual perspective, vestibular signals, and tactile input all play a role in the self-localization of a user inside a virtual body. With regards to agency, the “synchronicity of visuomotor correlations” is key. Finally, in terms of body ownership, “bottom-up” sensory information and “top-down” cognitive processes combine to produce the sense that the virtual body belongs to the user. The embodiment capabilities of VR have been associated with stimulating empathy, promoting prosocial values or realising long-term behaviour change (Versteeg, 2013).

However, as Madary and Metzinger (2016) point out, there may be “unexpected psychological risks if illusions of embodiment are misused, or used recklessly”. They suggest that “if we are interested in minimising potential damage and future psychosocial costs, these risks are themselves *ethically* relevant” (p. 5). Design methodologies which introduce ethically relevant issues early on in design and development can help to ensure that these concerns are considered and taken seriously by various stakeholders throughout the process, as we will return to below.

In addition to stimulating a sense of embodiment, VR systems also try to create a sense of immersion which is defined in terms of the technological qualities of IVRS; or the capacities of the technological medium to generate experiences that shut out physical reality (Slater & Wilbur, 1997). Levels of immersion can therefore differ significantly from one environment to another, depending on the technological affordances of the system. According to Slater and Wilbur (1997), a system is more likely to be immersive if it is vivid (in terms of multi-sensory modalities); extensive (in terms of congruence between the physical and virtual body); and if it contains strong plots and narratives (in terms of the credibility of the scenario, also referred to as the “plausibility illusion”). Characteristics used to gauge the extent of immersion therefore include display resolution, audio quality, frame rate, tracking, and field of view (Welch et al., 1996; Johnson and Stewart, 1999; Skalski and Whitbred, 2010; Cummings and Bailenson, 2016; Oh, Bailenson, and Welch, 2018). Media are considered more immersive when they provide “an inclusive, extensive, surrounding and vivid illusion of reality to the senses of a human participant” (Slater & Wilbur, 1997, p. 604). Though it is typically assumed that higher levels of immersion elicit higher levels of presence, Cummings and Bailenson’s (2016) meta-analysis of research in this area suggests that technological immersion has only a medium-sized effect on presence, where some system features (e.g. user-tracking and field of view) have a more significant impact than others (e.g. visual and auditory content).

Whereas immersion refers to the technological qualities of IVRS and is therefore considered an objective measure, presence refers to the psychological response of the user and is defined in terms of the “place illusion”, or the extent to which the user experiences the feeling of “being there” (Slater, 2009). An increased sense of presence is typically assumed to magnify user effects, meaning that the overall effectiveness of the mediated environment is increased (Slater & Wilbur, 1997; Nunez & Blake, 2001; Price & Anderson, 2006; Tamborini & Skalski, 2006; Tamborini & Bowman, 2010; Cummings & Bailenson, 2016). Presence can be defined according to three distinct subcategories (Lee, 2004; Oh, Bailenson & Welch, 2018). Telepresence refers to the extent to which the user feels present in the mediated environment (Steuer, 1994); self-presence refers to the extent to which the user experiences the virtual self as the actual self (Ratan & Hasler, 2009; Aymerich- Franch et al., 2012); and social presence refers to the extent to which the user has the sense of being with others (Biocca, 1997; Biocca & Harms, 2002, Biocca et al., 2003). Because studies have shown that social presence can have a positive impact on communication outcomes, VR researchers have tried to identify the immersive, contextual, and psychological factors that impact perceived social presence (Cummings and Wertz, 2018; Oh, Bailenson & Welch, 2018). Whereas maximising telepresence and self-presence is typically associated with making IVRS as technologically immersive as possible (e.g. the place illusion), social presence depends

more on the context and credibility of engagement (e.g. the plausibility illusion) (Oh, Bailenson & Welch, 2018).

Assuming that embodiment, immersion, and presence increases the effects of VR applications, each of these objectives needs to be considered in relation to the specific goals of different IVRS. Crucially, as Oh, Bailenson & Welch (2018) point out, we should not treat any one of these objectives as though it is an “absolute good”. More social presence may not always be better (Allmendinger, 2010). Depending on whether these environments are used for entertainment, learning, training, or therapy, it is critical to understand how these technologies mediate user experiences (Cummings and Bailenson, 2016).

Within VR, ethical concerns have arisen in relation to practical considerations. For example, with regards to simulation sickness, information overload, intensification of experience, and difficulties with re-entry into the real world (Behr et al., 2005). Additional ethical concerns have revolved around things like mental health issues, misrepresentation, immoral behaviour, implications for real-world behaviour, vulnerable populations, identity hacking, manipulation, exploitation, and desensitisation (see e.g. Slater et al, 2020; Spiegel, 2018; Kenright 2018; Pan et al., 2018; Chirokoff, 2017; Brey, 1999). So far, solutions to these problems have largely been based on technical interventions, making adaptations to the technology, the content, or the experimental design (Behr et al., 2005). But of course, as active mediators of experience these technologies require critical reflection and should not be evaluated solely in terms of their functionality (Versteeg, 2013).

6 Critical Concerns Regarding Emerging Ethical Issues

6.1 Affect, Persuasion, and Empathy

Similar to discussions in robot ethics, Burden and Savin-Baden (2019) suggest that when it comes to virtual humans, affective attachment is likely to be one of the strongest determinants of a user's experience. According to Meacham and Studely (2017), regardless of a robot's cognitive ability to care, through certain types of expressive movement they can still participate in the creation of caring environments, "irrespective of the existence of internal emotional states or intentions" (p. 98). VR environments also induce emotions in users, even when they are aware of their virtuality (Madary & Metzinger, 2016). Insofar as IVRS combine dynamic interaction and are immersive, convincing, and emotionally engaging they could be said to constitute a form of "persuasive media" (Cotton, 2021, p. 99).

Whilst concerns about data collection and privacy have been raised about all forms of information technology (van den Hoven et al., 2014), Ramirez et al. (2021) suggest that the "interactive and especially immersive nature of VR and AR technologies, and the degree to which they more greatly affect user emotions, makes such concerns especially important" (p. 19). With VR expanding rapidly into a range of different fields, concerns are growing regarding the privacy of data that is collected. According to Madary and Metzinger (2016), IVRS introduce new possibilities for "targeted advertising or 'neuromarketing'" (p. 18). IVRS open up both the type and quantity of information that private companies can obtain about individuals (Coyle & Thorson, 2001). For example, according to Bailenson (2018), in addition to "recording personal data regarding people's location, social ties, verbal communication, search queries, and product preferences, technology companies will also collect nonverbal behaviour - for example, user's posture, eye gaze, gestures, facial expressions, and interpersonal distance" (Bailenson, 2018). This non-verbal data can then be used diagnostically in terms of personal identity, medical conditions, and mental states (see Miller et al., 2020; Pfeuffer et al., 2019; Won et al., 2014). According to Madary and Metzinger (2016), privacy in the context of VR requires further attention given that avatars could be used as "humanoid interfaces" influencing consumer choice through real-time feedback; commercials in VR could feature the user themselves; and that "the use of big data to nudge users ("Big Nudging")... could have long-lasting effects, perhaps producing changes in user's mental mechanisms themselves" (p. 18).

Persuasive technologies are often created with the intent to promote prosocial values or instil long-term behaviour change (Berdichevsky & Neuenschwander, 1999). This is because, as Radiziwill (2019) points out, people respond to the "personalities" of computer interfaces, as well as to "psychological or social cues (such as praise of social pressure)" (p. 37). For this reason, VR applications are considered an especially good tool for nudging users "into being less racist, more sympathetic to homelessness, more caring about the environment, and to eating less meat" (Ramirez et al., 2020, p. 19).

According to Thaler and Sunstein (2009), a nudge is described as "any aspect of choice architecture that predictably alters people's behaviour without forbidding any options or

significantly changing their economic incentive” (p. 6). Nudging therefore relies on liberal and paternalistic principles, steering targets towards making decisions that are deemed most optimal. The term “digital nudging” is more recent and is defined as the “use of user-interface design elements to guide people’s behaviour in digital choice environments” (Weinmann et al., 2016). Whilst based on similar principles, the modality of digital nudging means that they provide more opportunities for choice architects (Meske et al., 2019). As nudging is not a value-free or neutral tool it is crucial to consider how and why certain values and norms come to be prioritised by choice architects.

Because of its persuasive capacity, VR has been used in journalism, fundraising, art, social justice movements, and as a therapeutic tool geared towards the promotion of long-term behaviour change. For example, the Horizon 2020 funded SOCRATES (Grant agreement ID: 951930) project is proposing conVRself, as a VR platform which can help patients tackle the root causes of their obesity. VR is also increasingly being used in order to “foster public empathy for the lived experience of marginalised, traumatised, or oppressed communities—including disaster victims, prisoners, refugees and children suffering extreme poverty and violence” (Cotton, 2021, p. 94). Bender & Broderick (2021) suggest that VR applications designed specifically with the goal of enhancing empathy are on the rise (see also Ventura et al., 2020). For example, VR training applications have been designed to stimulate empathy between healthcare providers and patients (Kleinsmith et al., 2015; Schutte & Stilić, 2017; Louie et al., 2018; Bertrand et al., 2018; Jütten et al., 2018), as well as to address inequalities about racism, inequity, and the impact of climate change on different populations (Roswell et al., 2020). Intervention-based approaches have also used VR scenarios to assess and enhance empathy in domestic violence offenders (Seinfeld et al., 2018) as well as to help improve police interrogation strategies (Kishore et al., 2022).

Because immersion and presence are both relevant to the social psychological phenomenon of construal levels—that is, the closer something is perceived to be to someone the more concrete it appears—VR is often positioned as a technology for “moral enhancement” that can improve the “empathy and moral imagination of the user” (Cotton, 2021, p. 107). However, according to Carter & Egilston (2020), the idea that VR mediates empathy and compassion for others has been the subject of much “uncritical industry boosterism around VR” (p. 25). Much of this attention derives from the notion that VR represents “the ultimate empathy machine” (a term coined by VR filmmaker Chris Milk).

It is important to note that empathy is a complex phenomenon that encompasses a variety of psychological processes “related to sharing and understanding the internal (mainly affective) mental states of other (not only human) beings” (Rueda & Lara, 2020, p. 5). According to Rueda & Lara (2020), there is a tendency within VR to focus on two types of empathy in particular: emotional empathy (in relation to personal distress) and perspective-taking (see e.g. Fisher, 2017; Ramirez, 2017; van Loon et al., 2018; Herrera

et al., 2018; Hamilton- Giachritsis et al., 2018; Francis et al., 2018; Seinfeld et al., 2018; Bailenson, 2018; Schoeller et al., 2019). The idea is that the immersive and embodiment

capabilities of VR stimulate an empathic response in the user by connecting them with a broader ethical dilemma (Cotton, 2021).

But as Rueda and Lara (2020) point out, there has been a “significant absence of consideration for the ethical aspects that arise from the aim of fostering empathy in these projects” (p. 11). Against this background, there has been growing criticism towards the claims of VR as an empathy generating machine (see Bender & Broderick, 2021; Carter & Egilston, 2020). Some have criticised the way in which the concept of empathy has been mobilised within VR (Bollmer, 2017), as well as the assumption that presence and a first-person perspective generates equivalent proximity with a subject (Hassan, 2020; Nash, 2017; Sutherland, 2015). Others have taken issue with the extent to which VR scenarios often emphasise suffering, putting the subject and VR participant in the relation of victim and bystander (Loh, 2017). Some argue that VR’s empathy narratives are undemocratic (Hassapopoulou, 2018), reinforcing existing stereotypes and reproducing power hierarchies (Heft-Luthy, 2019; Irom, 2018). What critical responses like these share is that they highlight the difficulty in disentangling the promises of persuasive technologies like VR from ethical concerns regarding equality and inclusivity.

6.2 Accessibility, Inclusion, and Exclusion

Gender and race are encoded into AI systems in a variety of ways (Geburu, 2020). From automatic gender recognition systems (Hamidi et al., 2018; Buolamwini & Geburu, 2018) to the names and voices of digital assistants like Siri and Alexa (Chambers, 2018), the very existence of these tools can serve to perpetuate harmful gender stereotypes. Within VR, there has already been a significant amount of discussion regarding gender-based discrimination, harassment and bias (see Carter & Egilston, 2020). One survey of VR users found that experiences of sexual harassment were not uncommon (Outlaw & Duckles, 2018), others have described specific instances of “virtual groping” (Belmaire, 2016) suggesting that virtual harassment has the potential for real harm as “unwanted [virtual] sexual advances are still both unwanted and sexual” (Cross, 2016). Danaher (2018) argues that virtual harassment can be considered sexual assault and that there therefore need to be clear and unambiguous means through which users can signal consent in IVRS (see also Wood et al., 2017).

According to Blackwell et al. (2019), it is both the interactive and immersive nature of VR, as well as a masculinised “gamer” culture that results in harassment being rife. They suggest that experiences of harassment are also “exacerbated by features such as synchronous voice chat, heightened feelings of presence and embodiment, and avatar movements that can feel like violations of personal space (such as simulated touching or grabbing)” (p. 100). Their survey of 25 social VR users demonstrates the extent to which definitions of what constitutes online harassment are typically subjective and highly personal. Counts of harassment fell into three categories: “*verbal harassment*, such as personal insults or hateful slurs; *physical harassment*, such as simulated touching or grabbing; and *environmental harassment*, such as displaying graphic content on a shared screen” (p. 101). Whereas much of the discussion concerning harassment refers to the interaction of human users, Franks (2017) outlines how engagements with IVAs are also problematic.

Other gender-related issues relate to the design of accessible VR in terms of both hardware and experience. For example, women have been found to be at greater risk of experiencing motion sickness (Munafo et al., 2017). Boyd (2014) explores the extent to which hormonal composition influences depth and perception cues, triggering physical side effects such as nausea, provocatively asking “is the Oculus Rift sexist?”

These considerations need to be kept in mind as the use of VR becomes more widespread in education and workplace training (Carter and Egilston, 2020). Peck, Sockol & Hancock (2020) argue that in order to mitigate bias, the VR community needs to tackle the underrepresentation of female participants and authors in VR research.

As VR spaces evolve, they run the risk of reproducing existing structural and systemic bias. For example, Cave and Dihal (2020) argue that the way in which intelligent machines are typically portrayed as white “in colour, ethnicity, or both” is illustrative not only of the milieu in which they are typically produced, but also of long-standing ideological structures that relate to race and technology. They describe “the prevalent Whiteness of real and imagined intelligent machines” across four categories: humanoid robots, chatbots and virtual assistants, stock images of AI, and portrayals of AI in film and television (p. 686). Numerous studies have shown the extent to which the racialisation of AI has exacerbated bias (see Ruane et al., 2019; Benjamin, 2019; Noble, 2018). For example, in systems that detect the skin tones of pedestrians (Hoffman & Morgenstern, 2019), in predictive policing systems (Richardson, Schultz & Crawford, 2019), in career ads in STEM (Lambrecht & Tucker, 2019), in recidivism algorithms (Angwin et al., 2016), in the politics of search engines (Itrona & Nissenbaum, 2000), in medical applications (Ferryman & Pitcan, 2018), in automatic speech recognition (Tatman, 2017), in chatbots (Schlesinger, O’Hara, & Taylor, 2018), and in hiring algorithms (Ajunwa et al., 2016). However in the VR community, discussions regarding features such as avatar design and virtual body-swapping have yet to consider race-related issues from an ethical point of view.

Within the literature on VR, another important theme on the topic of accessibility and exclusion is disability. Based on a survey of 79 VR users with disabilities around the world, Wong et al. (2017) suggest that mainstream VR technologies are often ableist and exclusionary in their design. Despite iterative design being an important principle within human-computer interaction (HCI), usability concerns that affect small populations have tended to be tacked on as an afterthought (Gerling & Spiel, 2021; Mott et al., 2019; Wong, Gillis & Peck, 2017). Mott et al. (2019) describe five key areas which the VR community should consider, including: “the accessibility of VR content, the accessibility of interaction techniques, device/hardware accessibility, inclusive user representations within VR environments, and accessibility-focused application areas for VR” (p. 451). However, despite the HCI research community beginning to address these issues through the development of VR systems for disabled people (see e.g. Snoswell & Snoswell, 2019; Zhao et al., 2019; Sayma et al., 2019; Bortone et al., 2018), Gerling and Spiel (2021) point out that the current generation of VR technologies are still largely designed for the “corporeal standard” (p. 12). They also highlight that focusing on basic barriers such as

practical accessibility fails to account for “the complexity of the relationship between a specific body and VR technology, the wider context in which disabled people experience VR, and the assumptions that VR technology makes about people’s bodies” (p. 1).

6.3 Phenomenology and Political Ontology: avenues of potential future investigations into the politics of VR and IVRS

6.3.1 *The realness of VR worlds*

The recent publication of David Chalmers’ *Reality+* (Chalmers, 2022) has reignited and broadened the discussion of some traditional philosophical problems in epistemology, philosophy of mind, and philosophy of consciousness, bringing them into dialogue with VR, VR experiences, and IVEs both actual and speculative. While many of these questions entail hypothetical scenarios, involving much more advanced and speculative forms of IVEs than are currently available, the questions raised are nonetheless relevant to the ethical consideration of current IVRS, and subsequently to the GuestXR project.

These questions extend the discussion of IVRS from ethics into the domain of phenomenological ontology (a study of what is qua what appears and how) and eventually political ontology (“claims or assumptions that a particular approach to social [or, by extension, political] enquiry makes about the nature of social [or political] reality—claims about what exists, what it looks like, what units make it up and how these units interact with one another”) (Blaikie, 1993). In a review of Chalmers (2022), philosopher of mind Tim Crane provides an overview of the issues raised in Chalmers’ philosophical treatment of VR: “Does it matter whether the “people” you interact with in a VR machine are real? Can things have real value in VR? Does the source of value come from experience or from our actual relations and interactions with people?” (Crane, 2022). Much of the discussion around Chalmers’ analysis centres on the reformulation of the classic Cartesian “evil genie” problem. The simulation problem qua update of the evil genie thought experiment is slightly different from the hypothetical question raised by VR: given a hypothetical IVE wherein we are not able to tell the difference between the IVE and physical reality (PR), (1) how would we know whether we were experiencing the IVRS or PR, and (2) how should we treat, epistemically, ethically and politically the experiences, particularly the experiences of value that we have in the IVRS.

The question about the realness of VR is often posed in terms of a normative question related to whether or not an experience is somehow “authentic”. From a phenomenological perspective, a philosophical approach that examines the structures of subjective experience, this question of “authenticity” is something of a red herring. There is no apparent reason to argue that experiences in IVRS are not real or authentic experiences in the relevant sense of the term. What is relevant is the different modalities by which objects appear within IVRS and PR. The object of experience e.g. a table in an IVRS may (will most certainly) however appear as different to the object of experience

of a table in PR in terms of how it is related both to the subject of experience, other objects in the environment and the perceptual environment itself. The experience of an object or another subject not being in PR does not make the experience or the object less authentic. In a similar way, a hallucination may appear as different to other objects in its perceptual environment, but it is still a real or authentic experience of a hallucination.

The phenomenological question of how objects or environments are experienced is somewhat complicated by what we can call, following Chalmers' "simulational realism" (Chalmers, 2022, p. xix), a virtual realism. Objects experienced in IVRS are experienced as real qua experience, but also as having an underlying (real) ontology composed of bits and code, as opposed to whatever metaphysical picture of the world is correlated with our experience of PR. That picture could be concordant with a "scientific" (up to date or not) world view, or another ontology. To put this another way PR and VR can both be considered as parts of phenomenological (experienced) reality, having differing, we could say, "regional" ontologies.

This idea of "regions" of experience shifts slightly in the case, raised by Chalmers (and Descartes), where there is not a distinguishable difference between PR and VR. In both cases it would be possible to have meaningful experiences as well as meaningful relations with both other humans represented by digital objects and digital objects that have been generated algorithmically and do not have any direct correlation in PR, for example the "Guest", or the environment itself. However, in the case where one region appears to us as indistinguishable from another, it is possible to raise the issue of error or deception, if the indistinguishability correlates with the intentions of other actors. Metzinger (2018) also raises concerns about "denying and confusing the ontological superiority of the world indexed as actual over a myriad of virtual ones. This levelling of value comes with a momentous belittlement of the historical process and of existence itself."

This also raises a somewhat similar question to the one posed by philosopher Robert Nozick (1974), where he asks why humans, presumably, have a preference for the trials and tribulations of "real life" as opposed to an ideal but simulated one inside a kind of experience machine. Nozick's thought experiment asks the question of what is it that we value about our experienced life over and above pleasure that would intuitively lead most, according to Nozick at least, to favour the struggles of real life over the pleasures of the "experience machine". The answer that Nozick provides has to do with agency, being able to shape the reality around ourselves, and the cultivation of ourselves according to evolving ideas of the kinds of people that we want to be (pp. 42-45).

Nozick's "experience machine" thought experiment is slightly different from Chalmers' living in a simulation experiment – in Nozick's experiment we have to think about why we would or would not climb into the machine, rather than thinking about the ontological, epistemic and ethical stakes of being in a simulation. In the case of the experience machine we have to consider giving up things that we care about, namely agency in relation to the world and ourselves as a kind of trade-off for pleasure. In the simulation thought experiment the question of agency is somewhat deferred as we do experience ourselves as having agency and exercising it, even if within a simulation. The two are again different from a situation wherein we spend time (perhaps increasingly so) in IVRS

while being conscious of the difference between our experiences in PR and VR. However, the thought experiments raise important ethical and political considerations that are salient in the present context of VR/IVE use.

6.3.2 Deception within IVRS

Most people seem to care about being deceived, especially when it relates to interactions with others. The deception concern has been raised and discussed at length in relation to social and care robotics (Meacham and Studley, 2017). In the case of VR, the more advanced the artificial agents we encounter in an IVRS, the greater the likelihood that we open ourselves up for deception insofar as we think ourselves to be interacting with someone or something that has a correlate in PR, when in fact we are not (Coeckelbergh, 2018). One approach to this would be for the development of “civil codes” within IVRS that would obligate artificial actors to be identified as such. This can also be legislated in national or European law. The text of the EU Digital Services Act (DSA) adopted by the European Parliament in January 2022 contains an amendment (No. 339) that proposes the following text:

Where a very large online platform becomes aware that a piece of content is a generated or manipulated image, audio or video content that appreciably resembles existing persons, objects, places or other entities or events and falsely appears to a person to be authentic or truthful (deepfakes), the provider shall label the content in a way that informs that the content is inauthentic and that is clearly visible for the recipient of the services.

This requirement is limited in the DSA to “very large online platforms”. A very large online platform is defined by the European Commission as having: “more than 45 million average monthly active users in the EU (which represents 10% of the 450 million consumers in the EU market)”¹. The DSA should come into force in 2023.

Delving into speculation again, such an idea might raise questions about the eventual rights of artificial agents, or why having a correlate in PR might be something that non-artificial agents should care about. Nor would obligations for the identification of artificial agents somehow rule out the possibility of meaningful experiences as well as meaningful relations with both other humans represented by digital objects and digital objects or environments that have been generated algorithmically and do not have direct physical reality correlates. It would raise questions about responsibility for the actions of artificial agents in IVRS.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/digital-services-act-ensuring-safe-and-accountable-online-environment_en

6.3.3 Privacy and Private government in and of IVRS

What remains a highly relevant ethical and political concern is control over construction, curation and control of digital objects and environments in IVRS and how possibilities for agency within an IVRS, including transformation of the fundamental rules of (various)

forms of engagement, are mediated politically (governance) and technically? In other words, how are IVRS governed and by whom? American political philosopher Elizabeth Anderson (2017) offers a distinction between “public” and “private” governance that is highly relevant to the political and technical governance of IVRS. Anderson offers the following definition of private government:

You are subject to private government wherever (a) you are subordinate to authorities who can order you around and sanction you for not complying over some domain of your life, and (b) the authorities treat it as none of your business, across a wide range of cases, what orders it issues or why it sanctions you. A government is private with respect to a subject if it can issue orders, backed by sanctions, to that subject in some domain of that subject’s life, and that subject has no say in how that government operates and no standing to demand that their interests be taken into account, other than perhaps in narrowly defined circumstances, in the decisions that government makes.

By this definition, private government can extend to spaces that are otherwise considered public either in the sense of being owned and controlled by the state, or being open and accessible to all. As commercial, social and political activity within IVRS becomes more commonplace, the question of private governance of such environments will become increasingly relevant.

By contrast to the notion of a lived environment (or part of an environment) being privately governed, the French philosopher Henri Lefebvre (1968) coined the expression *Le Droit à la Ville* (right to the city) to refer not only to the right to access to civic and public goods (e.g. rights), but also the right of residents to exercise collective power in transforming their lived environments. In a similar vein as the notion of private government, it is likely that the idea of a “*Droit à la Ville*” in IVRS will become increasingly relevant if and when VR use becomes increasingly prevalent and a more common medium of commercial, social, and political interaction.

The privateness of IVRS (in terms of ownership) potentially extends from a political to an ontological level. The experiential environment itself within an IVRS is potentially subject to private ownership and levels of control that seemingly extend far beyond PR, and with that the possibilities for transformation. This can be thought about in terms of property relations but also the kind of skills and capabilities necessary to engage in transformative activity within an IVRS.

These concerns about agency are closely linked to those regarding privacy and data-collection mentioned above. The accuracy of tracking and behavioural data in identifying users in VR has been argued to make anonymity virtually impossible (Miller et al., 2020; Pfeuffer et al., 2019). There is a long-standing discussion within political theory and political psychology concerning the importance of privacy (e.g. Westin, 2003) and more narrowly anonymity (Bachman et al., 2017; ref) for political agency. From a formal point

of view, the idea of ever increasing social transparency and granularity of information about the lives of subjects extending to physiology and behavioural minutiae as predictor

of social and political behaviour is closely linked to early theoretical articulations of totalitarian government.

7 Ethics by, in, and for Design

According to Gebru (2020), since 2019, “fairness and ethics have become safe-to-use buzzwords, with many in the machine learning community describing them as ‘hot’ topic areas” (p. 263). But, as she points out, ethical AI is not an abstract concept. Holistic, methodological approaches towards ethical AI need to be centred on who gets a seat at the table and who is involved in framing the goals and values. She argues that decolonising AI and making machine learning technologies more “fair” will necessarily involve more than just paying lip-service to diversity, inclusion, and ethics as the languages du jour.

As we have seen, in the context of discussions regarding AI and VR, the ethical debate has tended to focus on the “what” of ethics, rather than the “how” (Morley et al., 2019). Whilst formulating ethical principles is undoubtedly an important first step, the question which often follows is, how to “ensure and verify that an AI system actually respects these values?” (van de Poel, 2020, p. 387). In order to translate ethical principles into practice, methodologies are needed to elicit the values of relevant stakeholders and integrate those values at every stage of design and development. Crucially, as we have seen, it is not only a question of ensuring that IVRS respect existing or assumed values, but instead ensuring that there is a broad representation of diverse interests when values are discussed, both in terms of what values should be considered salient, as well as how those decisions should be made. In order to think about responsible development that constitutes more than just box ticking or the development of specific add-on features, various frameworks have emerged which can be used to promote ethics by, in, and for design (Dignum. 2018).

One of the main issues in the context of new and emerging technologies is how and when to start thinking about ethics. For example, in the context of IVAs, Reader and Savin-Baden (2019) suggest that one prominent issue is “how to engage and intervene in the developments that are yet to take place and how to influence or shape the values that will determine them” (p. 299). Whereas former approaches within safety engineering and machine ethics focused primarily on generating codes of conduct or guiding decision-making, approaches such as value sensitive design (VSD) consider the broader societal context, focusing on the integration of human values throughout the design and development process.

VSD is a “theoretically grounded approach to the design of technology that accounts for human values in a principled and comprehensive manner throughout the design process” (Friedman, Kahn Jr., and Borning 2006, p. 1). Having been developed initially in the field of human-computer interaction (HCI), Friedman and Hendry (2019) write that VSD “is intended to be useful no matter the particular socio-technical context of stakeholders,

values, and tools and technologies, from informed consent and web browsers to aesthetics and solar energy installations (p. 7). VSD is built around a tripartite methodology which involves conceptual investigations (e.g. identifying relevant

frameworks), empirical investigations (e.g. identifying stakeholder’s values), and technical investigations (e.g. considering the capabilities of the technology itself).

Whereas other approaches tend to prioritise the functionality and usability of innovations, VSD is a proactive, reflexive, and grounded methodology which can be harmonised with existing practices across diverse fields. Designed primarily as an anticipatory approach, VSD provides a means of identifying common values across diverse stakeholder groups; making value conflicts explicit and addressable, facilitating interventions at various stages of the process (Umbrello, 2019).

Of course the VSD approach is not without its shortcomings and challenges. Friedman et al. (2021) identify a number of “big problems and opportunities” confronting VSD, framing them as 8 grand challenges (see table 6).

Challenge	Key Questions
Accounting for Power	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which theories of power are well aligned for adoption or adaptation by value sensitive design? • What are appropriate methods (either existing, or to be developed) for identifying and potentially addressing power relationships influenced by the outcomes of design? • What are appropriate methods for identifying and potentially addressing power relationships throughout the process of design and design research? • What types of training and support will better position design researchers to identify, articulate and take responsibility for power dynamics in their work and the outcomes of their work? <p>How can value sensitive design be applied as a method for evaluation, review and exposure of power and technological relationships?</p>
Evaluating Value Sensitive Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What range of approaches could be employed for meaningful evaluation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What criteria or metrics could be employed to assess success or failure? ○ Given those criteria, what counts as evidence of success and failure? • How could a stock of value sensitive design case studies that illustrate successes and failures be developed, structured and presented so that the stock would be accessible to different audiences and communities? • How could value requirements for value sensitive design projects be formulated, particularly to account for value tensions? • How could value sensitive design projects be assessed for whether they realise their aims of supporting specific values? <p>What strategies could be utilised to evaluate the value sensitive design approach as a whole?</p>
Framing and Prioritising Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the role of ethical theory in the value sensitive design framework? • How does a researcher’s epistemological stance impact their interpretation and approach to value sensitive design regarding ethical framing, discovery of values, and choice of methods? • How can values be socialised as a portable conceptual entity, to be shared throughout the value sensitive design process, to stakeholders, across projects, and to influence those outside the value sensitive design community?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can the value sensitive design framework account for the transformation of values as the stakeholders' conceptualization and lived experiences of values changes? What is the impact of changing values over the course of a research initiative? Over a long period of time beyond the research project? <p>What are effective methods, best practices, and measures of evaluating approaches to framing and defining values?</p>
Professional and Industry Appropriation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can we embed value sensitive design with other work in computer ethics and engineering? What would a concrete holistic value sensitive design approach look like? <p>What knowledge and experience do we have for optimal project set-up?</p>
Tech Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can value sensitive design research and practice produce examples that can serve to broaden thinking about technology policy? How can policy discussions facilitate our ability to be critical of our own normative arguments? And how can value sensitive design bring new methods or ideas to policy discussions? In what ways might value sensitive design serve as a mechanism to challenge or make power structures visible, – especially those facilitated, established, or sustained by policy choices? How can we, as designers who engage explicitly with the relationship of values and design, impact policy in order to facilitate the work of value sensitive design? Specifically: How can designers impact policy? How can designers engage with policy scholarship, people, and ideas? How can designers engage policymakers in the research as sources of pertinent information, domain experts, and as more collaborative participants? From a value sensitive design perspective, is policy best viewed as another form of technology (or policy-making as a form of design)? How does thinking about policy-making in terms of design and vice versa re-shape either or both? How can engagement with technology policy inform the methods and theories used within the value sensitive design community? <p>How can policy questions and issues inform the work of value sensitive design and possibly move it forward in new directions?</p>
Values and Human Emotions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do we account for values vis-à-vis emotions? How are values grounded in non-rational (as opposed to irrational) aspects of human experience such as affect, feelings, moods, emotions and emoting? What is the role of emotion in judging “what people consider important in life”? What is the role that emotions play in shaping how values are performed and expressed in a particular context? <p>What methods do we need to carry out for more emotionally “sensitive” value sensitive design?</p>
Value Sensitive Design and Intelligent Algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How does a value sensitive design approach an analysis of value tensions in cases where asymmetric power relationships are amplified by ubiquitous intelligent algorithms? Can value sensitive design accommodate modelling intelligent algorithms as, say, technological stakeholders when they are embedded in multi-agent systems? How should technological stakeholders' values be balanced against human stakeholders' values, all other things being equal? How do we decide between the risk of breaking a complex “intelligent” system and allowing direct harm to some people? <p>What value sensitive design methods can be developed for the purpose of evaluating intelligent algorithms based on machine learning where the</p>

	traditional causal link between designers and the behaviour of their technologies has been eroded?
Value Tensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What methods exist to deal with value tensions within as well as outside the value sensitive design literature? • Can methods outside the value sensitive design literature, for example from philosophy and decision theory, enrich value sensitive design? • Are some values incommensurable and, if so, what are the implications for dealing with such value tensions in value sensitive design? • How can value sensitive design account for values that change over time and therefore create or alleviate value tensions? • How can stakeholders themselves recognize and balance value tensions? And how can we, as value sensitive design practitioners, help them to do so? • Does value sensitive design need an ethical theory to help solve value tensions? If so, who should bring in this ethical expertise and when in a value sensitive design project? • How do we recognize the most crucial value tensions in a value sensitive design project? • How do we prevent or deal with situations in which stakeholders fundamentally disagree with each other (for example because they have conflicting interests)? <p>Does lifting the debate to the level of values help when negotiating between conflicting interests?</p>

Table 6: 8 Grand Challenges for VSD from the 2016 Lorentz Workshop (Friedman et al., 2021)

The key questions outlined here constitute a valuable resource and should be considered thoroughly in any future application of VSD. Whilst all of the challenges discussed must be taken seriously, the framing and prioritisation of values and the extent to which the application of the VSD approach can be evaluated are long standing issues. In the context of developing IVRS, the question of VSD and intelligent algorithms is also particularly salient.

To date, the application of VSD to AI or VR are few and far between (see Alderwereld & Mioch, 2021). Studies include mapping ethical values to be incorporated into the design of intelligent assistive technology for dementia (Ienca et al., 2018); describing the translation of values into norms and then into design requirements using specific examples such as VR headsets (Gazzaneo et al., 2020); assessing the suitability of VSD in terms of coordinating the diverse stakeholders involved in AI research and development (Umbrello, 2019); investigating how the benefits and harms of AI can be understood in terms of where efforts geared towards making design and development more responsible tend to occur (Slota et al., 2020); articulating specific methodological steps with value sensitive elements in the redesign of a commercially available drone (Cawthorne & Robbins-Van Wynsberghe, 2020); and the design of a modified approach to VSD which specifically incorporates AI4SG principles (Umbrello and van der Poel, 2021).

Umbrello and van der Poel (2021) are particularly interested in AI technologies based on machine learning. This is because, as illustrated in the table above, these technologies present a specific challenge in that through their self-learning capabilities they are likely to acquire unforeseen or unintended features. They suggest that insofar as VSD is inherently self-reflexive and engages a broad array of stakeholders throughout the design process, the approach can be modified to deal with the specific challenges of AI design. Drawing upon recent work on AI4SG, they propose expanding the approach of VSD to include “a set of AI-specific design principles” (p. 284). They further outline how VSD in the context of AI must distinguish “between values promoted by design and values respected by design to ensure the resulting outcome does not simply avoid harm but also contributes to doing good” (p. 288). They also suggest that the VSD process be extended “to encompass the whole life cycle of an AI technology to be able to monitor unintended value consequences and redesign the technology as needed” (p. 288).

According to Umbrello and van der Poel (2021), VSD for AI can then proceed in four iterative phases. These phases include “context analysis” - understanding the normative starting point both conceptually and empirically; “value identification” - mapping a set of values which can form a starting point of the design process; “formulating design requirements” - translating values into design requirements; and “prototyping” – building tests that assess in how far the technology meets the design requirements regularly throughout the development process (pp. 289-290). It is worth pointing out that each of these phases may require a different combination of conceptual, empirical, and technological investigations. For example, understanding the ways in which different contextual variables potentially shape the ways in which values are understood requires both conceptual and empirical work, given the different socio-cultural and political norms at play in different contexts.

8 Conclusions

In this report, we have explored scholarly discussions surrounding the potential ethical implications of IVRS. This review is by no means exhaustive. We have not covered legal questions that arise in the context of IVRS, nor have we engaged with literature concerning the brain computer interface and neurotechnology or haptic technologies. However, as the GuestXR project unfolds, and additional relevant issues emerge, we will revisit and update this review accordingly (deliverables 5.6, 5.6, 5.12). What we have identified is a number of key discussions that should be taken into consideration from as early as possible in the design and development process. Having mapped these discussions across three core themes: ethical principles designed to shape design and development; technological affordances and related ethical concerns; and critical concerns regarding emerging ethical issues, we then speculatively introduced a number of political questions that may be raised by the pervasive use of IVRS for commercial, social and political interactions. Taken together, the ethical issues and questions addressed will be used to give shape to ongoing dialogues between partners within the GuestXR project as it unfolds. Through the course of this review, we have repeatedly stressed the importance of approaches that are commonly labelled as ethics by, in, and for design. This review will inform the development of deliverable 1.1 (Guidelines for ethics-by-design), where the VSD methodology introduced will be modified, utilised, and developed within the context of the GuestXR project.

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